

ATTENTION OF MEDICAL STUDENTS TO THE ISSUE OF TECHNICAL SAFETY

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Mamutova Peruza

NSPI Zoology, teacher of the department of human morphophysiology and teaching methods

Rajabova Iroda

4th grade student of the Karakalpakstan Medical Institute

Mamutov Sharafatdin

Head of the Pathology Department of Karakalpakstan Medical Institute, candidate of medical sciences

Abstract:

Keywords:

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Introduction. One of the priority tasks of every state policy is to achieve the highest level of public health care. To reach this peak, one of the most important tasks before the state and the system is to provide the industry with modern medical technical equipment [1]. Indeed, today's medicine cannot be imagined without technical equipment. This not only provides a number of conveniences and certainties in medicine, but also creates a new problem in the process of medical activity, that is, the problem of equipment safety [2]. Therefore, in the process of training medical personnel, there is a need to focus on the issues of equipment safety. In addition, according to the reports of the World Health Organization, more than 2 million people die every year due to non-compliance with the safety rules of equipment [3].

Purpose of work. To listen to the opinions of the students studying at the junior level of the medical institute on the safety of equipment in medicine and to analyze the changed attitude of the students towards these rules after the rules and importance of equipment safety were explained to them. Also, comparing the results of the analysis with the results of other studies.

Sources and methods. 300 students studying at the 3rd stage of treatment, pediatrics, medical prevention, medical biology and stomatology at the Karakalpakstan Medical Institute and the results of the questionnaire from them served as the object of investigation. At first, students' opinions about the safety of equipment in medicine were heard, and at the same time, the rules of equipment safety were explained to students in the pathological physiology class [4]. After that, questionnaires were distributed to students on this topic and the results were analyzed.

Inspection results and their discussion. During the 2022-2023 academic year, 506 students studied at the 3rd stage of the Karakalpakstan Medical Institute, and the students who participated in the survey make up 75.7% of all students studying at the 3rd stage in this academic year. When the participants of the survey were asked verbally what method they would use to ensure the safety of the equipment in the future, before being given an understanding of technical equipment, almost all students gave the answer that they should be as far away from technical equipment as possible. and the remaining 1.2% of students said that they could not say anything about it. When these results are compared with the results of articles from other sources, it can be seen that similar results are observed in them [5].

There was a need to evaluate how much their opinions changed after the rules on safety of equipment were explained to students according to the same criteria [6]. Therefore, the following to the students; 1. Which method did you favor following to ensure the safety of equipment until today; 2. Did you change your mind after the topic of technical safety was explained; 3. If your opinion has not changed, how do you explain it; 4. If you have changed your mind, which type of equipment security did you choose; 5. Say the name of the security of the chosen technique; 6. A questionnaire containing questions such as why you changed your mind and chose this method of technical safety was distributed [7]. When the results were discussed, 52% of the students who took part in the survey said that in the future they had the idea of using constructive measures in the implementation of technical safety, and 61% of them said that this method is to keep technical equipment as far as possible from medical personnel. 39% of students said that it was favorable for them and therefore changed their initial opinion, while the remaining 39% of students changed their initial opinion to a constructive measure of technical safety due to the fact that the condition of covering the network chain with an enhanced protective coating is favorable. stated that it has changed the quality related to the application of measures. When analyzing sources and articles related to research in this regard, it became clear that there are different opinions [8]. 41% of the students who participated in the survey changed their opinion to the need to apply organizational measures in the implementation of equipment safety, and 59% of students cited the need to explain the rules of equipment safety to medical personnel in a timely manner as the reason for this opinion. and another 40% of students agreed that in addition to this, medical personnel should be taught and required. In particular, it should be noted that the views related to this item are consistent with the results of a number of other studies [9]. The remaining 6% of the students who participated in the survey changed their opinion that technical measures should be regarded as superior in the implementation of technical safety, and explained that they came to this opinion with the importance of periodic

control of technical safety. It should be noted that 2% of the students who participated in the survey did not change their initial opinion even after being given explanations on the safety of equipment. They cited as the reason that they believe that a narrow range of specially recommended methods of equipment safety should be used. It can be observed that different sources have different information about special methods of technical safety in a narrow range [10].

Conclusion. After each topic that is taught to students, their opinions about it change rapidly. Students expressed interest in modern requirements based on more traditional methods in matters of technical safety in medicine. As new technologies appear in medicine, new requirements for equipment safety appear. At this point, it should be noted that the main conditions of equipment safety include keeping them in a clean and technically adjusted condition, following the rules of use (when, how long, in what condition), and knowing how to properly direct the voltage in them. Deeper teaching of these skills to students is the demand of the times, and it will certainly bring practical results.

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